

Synergizing Medicinal Herbs for Sustainable Eco-friendly Herbal Healthcare Textile Products

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Abstract:

Musculoskeletal disorders represent a prevalent global health concern, necessitating effective and sustainable solutions for symptom alleviation and improved quality of life. The paper explores the extraction and analysis of medicinal herbs, with a specific emphasis on their utilization in creating herbal finished textile products. These products are designed to cater to musculoskeletal disorders while aligning with eco-friendly materials, ensuring minimal environmental impact and promoting overall well-being. By combining the inherent therapeutic properties of medicinal herbs with sustainable practices, this study aims to contribute to a more environmentally conscious and holistic approach to managing musculoskeletal disorders.

Keywords: *Ecofriendly materials, herbs, herbal dyeing, musculoskeletal disorders, Sustainable products.*

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1. Introduction

Sustainability, a complicated, multifaceted notion, considers the effects on the economy, society, the environment, and human health. From the beginning of time, the traditional and ancient Indian medical systems of Ayurveda, Siddha, Yoga, and Unani have been providing people with healthcare solutions. Ayurveda has been a part of India's rich culture and history since the dawn of time. Even though Ayurveda use has been declining in recent years, its therapeutic applications have lately experienced a resurgence, and the western world has accepted it considering the answers it provides to a variety of healthcare concerns [1]. The utilisation of natural items with plant, animal, or mineral origins forms the basis of all this holistic medical approach and offers many sustainable solutions [2]. Plant-based ingredients make about 90% of Ayurvedic preparations, which helps regulate the doshas and reverse pathophysiological conditions [3].

According to World Health Organisation, 80% of people globally rely on traditional medical systems for some part of their basic healthcare need and around 21,000 plant species have the potential to be utilised as medicinal plants. 65 percent of the population in India depends on traditional medicines for healthcare solutions. Treatment with herbal remedies is seen to be quite safe as there are either no or relatively few adverse reactions [4]. Ayurveda is a holistic approach to health and personalised medicine. The rising adverse effects of synthetic pharmaceuticals, the absence of effective treatments for many chronic conditions, the high cost of new medications, microbial resistance, developing disorders, etc. have all boosted public interest in complementary and alternative medicine [5].

One of the major occupational healthcare problems is Musculoskeletal Disorders or MSDs. Musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) are a broad category of disorders that can affect any part of the musculoskeletal system, such as the muscles, bones, joints, spinal discs, supporting blood vessels, and connective tissues including tendons, ligaments, and cartilages [6]. These are normally degenerative disorders and worsens over time if not treated on time properly.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Fabric selection

Hundred per cent bamboo (100% B) and hundred per cent wool (100%W) yarns were taken for the study. The selection of these yarns is based on their inherent characteristics of comfort, breathability, and eco-friendliness [7]. The hundred per cent yarns selected were blended with cotton in the ration 50:50 to get blended yarns namely 50:50 cotton bamboo (50:50CB), 50:50 cotton wool (50:50CW) The four selected yarns were subjected to yarn strength and yarn elongation tests. The developed hundred per cent and 50:50 blend yarns were then converted into fabric by handloom, powerloom and knit method of fabric construction. The nomenclature of the developed materials is given in Table 1.

Table 1 - Nomenclature of the Developed Fabrics

Handloom Fabrics		Powerloom Fabrics		Knit Fabrics	
100% pure	50:50 Blend	100% pure	50:50 Blend	100% pure	50:50 Blend
Bamboo (HB)	Cotton Bamboo (HCB)	Bamboo (PB)	Cotton Bamboo (PCB)	Bamboo (KB)	Cotton Bamboo (KCB)
Wool (HW)	Cotton Wool (HCW)	Wool (PW)	Cotton Wool (PCW)	Wool (KW)	Cotton Wool (KCW)

2.2 Selection of Disease conditions

Musculoskeletal disorders refer to a range of conditions that affect the muscles, bones, joints, tendons, ligaments, and other supporting structures of the body [8]. Disease conditions like knee pain, elbow pain, heel pain and wrist pain were taken for the study.

2.3 Selection, extraction and optimization of medicinal herbs

Medicinal herbs namely Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia, and Terminalia Chebula were taken to study the properties of each herb and to understand its effectiveness in treating musculoskeletal disease conditions. The selected three medicinal herbs were taken separately, dried, grinded under hygienic conditions and the powder obtained was subjected to ethanolic extraction. Phytochemical screening test of the extracted medicinal herbs were done to identify the secondary metabolites present in each one of them. The extracts of the herbal solutions were taken in four different proportions namely 1:1:1, 1:2:1, 1:2:3 and 2:3:2 and subjected to antibacterial activity to select the best proportion for herbal dyeing. FTIR Spectroscopy was performed on the selected optimized ratio to find out the functional groups present in the medicinal herbal combination.

2.4 Application of the optimized herbal extracts to the developed fabrics

The selected optimized herbal extracts were applied to the developed hundred per cent and blended bamboo and wool fabrics of handloom, powerloom and knit by dip pad dry method and microencapsulation methods. The original and dyed fabrics were subjected to visual inspection to evaluate the colour, texture, lustre, odour and general appearance. The developed microencapsulated fabrics were subjected to SEM analysis to study the fixation of the dye.

2.5 Developing herbal finished products for musculoskeletal disorders

The hundred per cent and 50:50 blend handloom, powerloom and knit herbal finished dip pad dry and microencapsulated bamboo and wool fabrics were used for developing healthcare products like knee band for knee pain, elbow brace for elbow pain, wrist band for wrist pain and heel wrap for heel pain. The developed herbal finished products were evaluated for its performance by wear study among the selected patients.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of Yarn strength and Elongation

The results of the yarn strength and yarn elongation of 100% B, 100%W, 50:50 CB and 50:50 CW is given in Table 2.

Table 2 - Yarn strength and Yarn Elongation of Selected yarns

Name of the Spun Yarns	Single Yarn Strength		Single Yarn Elongation	
	Avg. Strength (g/tex)	CV% of Strength	Avg.% Elongation	CV % of Elongation

100% B	353.5	6.59	14.91	5.75
100% W	954.7	13.42	13.58	15.52
50:50 CB	285.7	6.12	13.45	10.11
50:50 CW	765.8	12.14	9.56	10.45

The results from Table 2 indicates that all the spun yarns had good strength and elongation which makes it suitable for weaving and knitting operations. Hundred percent wool and wool cotton blend yarns exhibited good strength and elongation when compared to hundred per cent bamboo and bamboo and bamboo cotton blends.

3.2 Phytochemical screening analysis of selected medicinal herbs

The Phytochemical analysis of the selected medicinal herbs Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia and Terminalia Chebula given in Table 3.

Table 3 - Phytochemical Analysis of Selected Medicinal Herbs

Selected Medicinal Herbs	Phytochemical Screening Tests								
	Alkaloids			Flavonoids	Glycosides	Saponins	Tannins and Phenols		Sterols and Terpenoids
	Maye r's Test	Wagne r's Test	Dragondroff's Test	Shinoda Test	Salkowski's Test	Froth Test	Le ad Ace tate Test	Fe rric Chloride Test	Libermann Burchard Test
Ricinus Communis	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+
Holoptelea Integrofolia	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Terminalia Chebula	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Note: + present - Absent									

The results from the phytochemical screening of the selected medicinal herbs indicates that all the medicinal herbs are good in advantageous phyto-constituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, phenols, sterols and terpenoids. Flavonoids present in Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia, Terminalia Chebula, indicated the herbs potential as anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, cardio-protective, anti-ageing, anti-cancer, and anti-diabetic activities [9]. Glycosides are detected in Terminalia Chebula. Tannins, phenols and saponins are known to be anti-microbial, anti-fungal anti-inflammatory, neuro protective and destressing agents. Terminalia Chebula can also be used as natural mordant besides its medicinal properties.

3.3 Analysis of Antibacterial Activity of the selected Medicinal Herbs

The anti-bacterial test was performed on pure handloom 100% HB, 100% HW, 50:50 HCB and 50:50 HCW blend fabrics as handloom fabrics consists of same type of yarn in both warp and weft directions. Agar Diffusion Test was conducted using Bacillus Subtilis (Gram Positive) organism and Escherichia coli (Gram Negative) micro-organisms for the selected herbal combination in four ratios 1:1:1, 1:2:3, 3:2:1 and 2:3:2 respectively for Escherichia Coli (gramnegative bacteria) and Bacillus Subtilis (gram positive bacteria). The results of antibacterial activity for the selected medicinal herbal combination consisting of Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia and Terminalia Chebula (RiC, HI, TC) to optimize the herbal ratios 1:1:1, 1:2:3, 3:2:1 and 2:3:2 is recorded in Table 4 and Fig.1.

Table 4 – Analysis of Antibacterial Activity of Selected Medicinal Herbs

RiC, HI, TC in ratios	ZONE OF INHIBITION (in mm) FOR HCB- RiC, HI TC									
	Escherichia Coli (Gram -ve bacteria)					Bacillus Subtilis (Gram +ve bacteria)				
	100% HB	100% HW	50:50 HBC	50:50 HWC	100% HB	100% HW	50:50 HBC	50:50 HWC	50:50 HMC	
1:1:1	25	35	33	30	32	40	33	38	36	
1:2:3	25	28	25	40	30	36	35	33	38	
3:2:1*	35	45	35	43	35	42	37	43	44	
2:3:2	27	38	32	26	34	37	36	38	38	

Figure 1 - Analysis of Antibacterial Activity of Selected Medicinal Herbs

The results from Table 4 reveals that among the four ratios 1:1:1, 1:2:3, 3:2:1 and 2:3:2 of herbal combination, comprising of Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia and Terminalia Chebula, the highest zone of inhibition is displayed in the ratio 3:2:1 for all the treated 100% HB, 100% HW and 50:50 HBC, 50:50 HWC pure and blend handloom fabrics for Escherichia Coli (gram negative) and for Bacillus Subtilis (gram positive) respectively (Fig 2, Fig 3). Hence for Knee pain, Tennis Elbow pain, Heel pain and Wrist pain, the selected medicinal herbs Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia and Terminalia Chebula in the optimized ratio 3:2:1 was selected for herbal dyeing.

Figure 2 - Antibacterial Activity of Gram-Positive Bacteria in the Ratio 3:2:1

Figure 3 - Antibacterial Activity of Gram-Negative Bacteria in the Ratio 3:2:1

3.4 FTIR Spectroscopy of selected Medicinal Herbs

The results of FTIR spectrum of the selected herbal combination for the optimized ratio 3:2:1 is given in Fig.4 and the functional groups identified are given in Table 4

Figure 4 - FTIR Spectroscopy of Optimized ratio 3:2:1

Table 5 - FTIR Spectral Peak Values and Functional Groups

RiC, HI, TC in 3:2:1 Ratio		
Peak values	Groups	Compound class
2936	C-H stretching	Alkane group
2844	N-H stretching	Amine Salt
3243	C-H stretching	Alkyne group
1710	C=O stretching	Conjugated aldehyde
1600	C=C stretching	Conjugated alkene
1450	C-H bending	Alkane

From Fig.4 and Table 5, it is observed that the extracts of herbal combinations consisting of Ricinus communis, Holoptelea Integrofolia and Terminalia Chebula in the ratio 3:2:1 exhibited characteristic bands at 2936cm⁻¹, 2844 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of alkane group and amine salt. The characteristic band 3242cm⁻¹ shows presence of alkyne group, the wavelengths 1710cm⁻¹, 1600cm⁻¹ and 1450cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of aldehyde, alkene and methyl group.

3.5 Analysis of Visual Evaluation of original and Treated Handloom, Powerloom and Knit Fabrics

The results of visual inspection was conducted for original (O), dip - pad dry (D) and microencapsulated (M) treated samples with herbal combination Ricinus Communis, Holoptelea Integrifolia, and Terminalia Chebula is given in Table 6.

Table 6 - Visual Inspection of Handloom, Powerloom Knit Original and Treated fabrics

VISUAL EVALUATION OF H, P, K DIP PAD DRY FABRICS													VISUAL EVALUATION OF H, P, K MICROENCAPSULATED FABRICS														
H, P, K Dip pad dry fabrics	Colour			Texture			Lusture			Odour		Appearance		H, P, K Microencapsulated Fabrics	Colour			Texture			Lusture			Odour		Appearance	
	Good	Fair	Poor	Soft	Medium	Rough	High	Medium	Dull	Pleasant	Unpleasant	Even	Uneven		Good	Fair	Poor	Soft	Medium	Rough	High	Medium	Dull	Pleasant	Unpleasant	Even	Uneven
100% HB ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% HB ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
100% HW ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% HW ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 HBC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 HBC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 HWC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 HWC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
100% PB ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% PB ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
100% PW ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	80	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% PW ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 PBC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 PBC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 PWC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	80	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 PWC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
100% KB ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% KB ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
100% KW ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	100% KW ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 KBC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 KBC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-
50:50 KWC ^D	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	100	-	50:50 KWC ^M	100	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	100	-	100	-

The feedback received for visual evaluation of H, P, K dip pad dry (D) and micro encapsulated (M) fabrics from Table 5 reveals that, the handloom, powerloom and knit dip pad dry and microencapsulated fabrics were good in color, soft in texture, high in lusture and had pleasant odour. The general look of the dip pad dry and micro encapsulated treated fabrics altogether had evenness in appearance.

3.6 SEM Analysis of Microencapsulated Fabrics

Handloom (H) and knit (K) materials consisted of the same type of yarn in both warp and weft, wales and course directions. Hence to understand the binding of herbal microcapsules to the fabric surfaces, handloom fabrics in the optimized ratio 3:2:1 were subjected to SEM analysis to confirm the binding of microcapsules. The results (Fig.5) revealed that 100% HB, 100% HW images revealed the herbal deposition on the surface of the fabrics with some protruding fibres and gap in the capsules whereas the handloom blend fabrics, 50:50 HBC, 50:50 HWC showed a uniform deposition of the herbal capsules with a reduced pore size on the surface of the fabrics.

Figure 5 - SEM Analysis of Microencapsulated Fabrics

3.7 Aesthetic and Performance Analysis of Developed Healthcare Herbal Dyed Products

3.7.1 Aesthetic Evaluation

The developed herbal healthcare products aesthetic properties like design, comfort of wearing the product, texture and suitability of the product to the ailments were evaluated by the selected patients. The results are given in Table 7.

Table 7 - Aesthetic Evaluation of the Developed Herbal Health Care Products

Evaluation of Aesthetic Properties of the Developed Herbal Healthcare Products												
Healthcare Products	Handloom (H)				Powerloom (P)				Knit (K)			
	Design	Comfort	Texture	Suitability of the Product	Design	Comfort	Texture	Suitability of the Product	Design	Comfort	Texture	Suitability of the Product
Knee Pad	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5
Elbow Wrap	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5
Heel Wrap	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5
Wrist Band	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5

Key: Excellent-5, Very Good-4, Good-3, Fair-2, Poor-1

From Table 6, it is noted that the design and suitability of the handloom, powerloom and knit healthcare products were ranked as excellent whereas the texture and comfort of wearing the healthcare products were rated as very good by all the subjects for all the treated products.

The developed herbal dyed handloom (H), powerloom (P) and knit (K) herbal healthcare products were given for wear study to ten selected patients, each having the respective ailments, in consultation with a doctor. The wear study on selected patients with the respective disease conditions was carried on after getting approval from the Ethical Committee. The products were given to selected patients and were asked to wear the product for a specific time duration and the results were recorded.

The evaluation of wear study of dip pad dry and microencapsulated knee pads for knee pain (Sample Fig.6) made from handloom, powerloom and knit fabrics reveal that, hundred per cent subjects revealed that after using the treated knee pads for a period of one month for eight hours from 8 am to 5 pm there was a considerable reduction in the knee pain and stiffness felt in the knee was reduced. All the subjects remarked that while using the product and afterwards, there was an improvement in walking without stiffness and pain. The results of the wear study for Elbow brace for Tennis Elbow (Sample Fig.7) shows that all the subject had a considerable reduction of pain in the elbow and stiffness while moving the elbow joint was reduced. Hundred per cent subjects were of opinion that after using the treated handloom, powerloom and knit elbow braces for one month for eight hours, the elbow joints were movable without much pain and there was improvement in the flexibility of the hand.

The wear study of heel wrap for heel pain made from dip pad dry and microencapsulated handloom, powerloom and knit fabrics for heel pain (Sample Fig.8) reveal that there was a reduction of pain in the heel, early morning stiffness and pain was considerably reduced for all the subjects. Hundred percent subjects were of opinion that there was an average improvement in the reduction of pain while standing for long period of time after using the product for eight hours for one month. The results of the wear study of the wrist band for wrist pain (Sample Fig.9) shows that all the subjects observed that there was a considerable reduction of pain in the wrist area and stiffness of the wrist was reduced after using the herbal finished handloom, powerloom and knit products for a period of eight hours for one month. All the patients revealed that there was improvement in the flexibility of finger from where the pain was feeling.

Figure 6 - Knee Pad

Figure 7 - Elbow Brace

Figure 8 – Heel Wrap

Figure 9 – Wrist Band

All the developed herbal healthcare products for the selected disease conditions such as Knee pad for knee pain, Elbow brace for Tennis elbow, Heel cover Heel pain, Wrist band for Wrist pain with suitable herbal combinations performed well on the subjects chosen with the respective ailments. All the subjects preferred to use herbal microencapsulated products more than dip pad dry products as they showed considerable reduction of symptoms related to specific ailment.

4. Conclusion

One of the main issues on which the world is currently focusing is sustainability. Environmental sustainability may be accomplished by manufacturing products without disrupting or harming the earth's biological equilibrium [10]. Using herbal textile products can make a significant contribution to the textile industry's environmental sustainability. Ancient scholars were of opinion that medicinal herbs are the only way to cure diseases and regain health. The herbal healthcare products were made from hundred per cent and blend eco-friendly fabrics which were finished with extracts of medicinal herbs. The herbal products were safer to use, didn't cause any harm to the individuals and performed well, revealing the properties of the medicinal herbs and textile materials it were made of. The wellness of the herbal healthcare products developed smoothed the soul, contributed to sustainability, developed eco-consciousness, and gave relief to the body.

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